

THE DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF A HANDHELD COMBINED RAMAN-XRF SYSTEM FOR FUTURE LUNAR ASTRONAUTS. H. N. Lerman¹, I. B. Hutchinson¹, M. McHugh¹, J. Jones¹, H.G.M. Edwards¹, C. Murgatroyd¹, J. Strachan-Deol¹, R. Agrawal¹, M. Roos¹, J. Holtom¹, S. Wedge¹, A. Moral², C. Perez², L. Purrinos², P. Perez², M. Benito², J. Zafra², M. Santamaria², O. Prieto Ballesteros³, A. Higginson⁴, Y. Brown⁴, J. Manrique⁵, G. Lopez-Reyes⁵, I. Drozdovskiy⁶, A. Ball⁷, J. Parnell⁸, J. Armstrong⁸

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PHOENIX for PANGAEA: Human missions to the Moon and Mars are the next step in both ESA and NASA planetary exploration roadmaps. During such missions, astronauts will be required to perform geological analyses as part of surface characterisation and resource utilisation mapping.

PANGAEA (Planetary Analogue Geological and Astrobiological Exercise for Astronauts) is ESA's astronaut training programme which aims to provide astronauts with the fundamental knowledge and training to become field scientists during future lunar (and Mars) exploration missions [1]. To aid with training (and ultimately surface operations), two PHOENIX (Portable Handheld cOmbinEd Raman-LIBS-XRF) spectrometers have been developed as fast and real-time tools for in situ geological and mineral analysis [2]. The PHOENIX spectrometers for PANGAEA are composed of two breadboards which integrate different analytical techniques. The first breadboard (BB1) incorporates a Raman spectrometer and a Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) [3]; and the second breadboard (BB2) a Raman and X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) spectrometer – see Figure 1.

Here, we present the design, development, and testing in a simulated lunar environment of the PHOENIX Raman-XRF prototype handheld system and discuss the performance of the instrument in the context of lunar analogue sample testing.

Figure 1: The BB2 prototype, combining Raman spectroscopy, XRF, and context imaging (the sub-systems are integrated in a handheld Instrument

Head and Main Body, both connected via a flexible Harness Connection Hose).

Lunar science goals: The breadboards will help to achieve seven science objectives regarding the in-situ characterization of the geochemistry and mineralogy of lunar rocks; these are to:

1. Quickly distinguish olivine, pyroxenes and amphiboles, which display the same primary elements but different crystalline structures (Si, O, Mg, Fe, etc.);

2. Detect endmembers of felsic solid solutions such as plagioclases;

3. Distinguish endmembers of mafic solid solutions (i.e., fayalite from forsterite and others);

4. Distinguish and classify different chondrites, iron and stony-iron meteorites;

5. Distinguish calcium–aluminium-rich inclusion (CAI) and the presence of hydrated carbonaceous material on meteorites;

6. Distinguish the presence of volatile either on regolith or trapped in pyroclastic glasses;

7. Evaluate relative elements abundances of the outcrop/regolith, including for ISRU evaluation (i.e., titanium or other useful materials content in the regolith).

Instrument Design: The BB2 breadboard instrument consists of two systems: the Instrument Head (which incorporates subsystems required for in-situ measurements), and the Main Body.

The Instrument Head incorporates the XRF sub-system (an Amptek X-ray Tube used to generate the primary X-rays, and an Amptek SDD that images the secondary X-rays produced by the target material); the context imaging subsystem (an Allied Vision Mako colour-camera and set of optics); and the Raman excitation and collection optical sub-system. It also comprises a Human Machine Interface (HMI) subsystem, which is composed of a screen used to check the system status, a baffle, and several key switches and LEDs that ensure the system can be handled in a safe manner. This system also includes an instrument status indicator and a trigger for initiating the measurement cycle.

The Main Body incorporates the components of the Raman subsystem that are not required for in-situ measurements (i.e., a 532nm laser and the spectrometer); an onboard data handling subsystem (that controls the overall operational performance of the breadboard, and operates the laser, spectrometer, and XRF and camera subsystems); and the power and communication subsystems. As with the Instrument Head, the Main Body incorporates an HMI subsystem, which includes key switches and LEDs to ensure the system can be properly activated, sockets to provide power from an external power supply (if needed), a screen for monitoring the data, and straps so that it can be carried on a back.

LUNA Campaign: The PHOENIX team have been involved in a series of field studies in order to optimize the design and operation of the breadboard instruments. Most recently, the teams took part in a campaign at ESA's and DLR's LUNA analogue facility (part of the European Astronaut Centre, located in Cologne, Germany) in order to demonstrate the feasibility of an astronaut (in an EVA suit) using the breadboards in a simulated lunar environment.

During the campaign, spectra and context images were acquired from a range of lunar analogue samples located at different heights (in order to assess the accessibility of the samples by the instrument user).

The BB2 instrumentation was assessed in terms of the breadboard's ability to detect and characterize lunar minerals (such as pyroxenes, feldspars and olivines), as well as evidence of resources valuable to astronauts (such as water). An evaluation of the breadboard was also performed in terms of ergonomics/usability by the astronaut in a representative suit. The results from this campaign are summarised in this presentation.

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References: [1] Sauro F. et al. (2023) *Acta Astronautica*; 204, 222-238. [2] Seoane L. et al. (2023) *Seventh edition of the Spanish Meeting of Planetary Sciences and Exploration of the Solar System*; 7th CPESS. [3] Moral A. et al. (2025) *JRS*, 56, 11.